

The five dilemmas of interdisciplinary research and how to deal with them: a review

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ABSTRACT

Interdisciplinary research receives increasing attention from academics, research organizations, and funding bodies. It is seen as a promising avenue to develop novel insights. However, it is also considered to be more complicated to set up and to conduct successfully. To make the scattered literature on the subject accessible and to derive implications for both individual researchers and policy makers, we propose that interdisciplinary research can be conceptualized as a set of five dilemmas. Based on an extensive and systematic literature review of 137 research articles we present these dilemmas to better structure the main promises and pitfalls of interdisciplinary research. The value of conceptualizing interdisciplinary research this way is three-fold: (1) it makes existing research on the topic accessible as it structures the highly dispersed debates, (2) it provides implications for individual researchers active in an increasingly interdisciplinary academic environment, and (3) it supports research organizations and funding bodies in developing strategies to support an interdisciplinary research ecosystem. We also present a data preprocessing, exploration, and analysis framework in later sections of the report. This technical framework is aimed at accelerating studies of interdisciplinarity (and for testing our framework in follow-up studies) by streamlining common tasks such as data cleaning and enrichment, and automatic detection of interdisciplinary bodies of work in large bibliometric databases.

Keywords: *interdisciplinary research, systematic review, scientometrics, linked data*

1 INTRODUCTION

In light of increasing collaboration and complex research questions interdisciplinarity has become a major trend in academia.

Many novel insights only came to be because researchers from different fields found a way to work together. And therefore research organizations and funding bodies promote interdisciplinary research (IDR) and individual researchers are interested in conducting it. Much research has focused on exploring IDR itself, conditions in which it works and in which it does not, promising approaches and failed initiatives. However, these findings are scattered across fields and unapproachable for those interested in their implications. With this article we condense the most important findings on IDR and present them as a set of five dilemmas, highlighting that the promises of IDR are in constant tensions with possible downsides. Understanding interdisciplinary research as a set of dilemmas will help research organizations and individual researchers to better navigate the challenge of conducting IDR successfully.

It is frequently echoed that IDR creates new knowledge and ideas (Choi & Pak 2008), that it challenges the status quo (Corbett et al. 2013) and that it is therefore “a source of creativity and innovativeness” (Yegros-Yegros et al. 2015). Moreover, IDR is characterized as problem-centered and therefore allows researchers to address problems at the intersections of disciplines (e.g., Braun & Schubert 2003; Barry et al. 2008; Bammer 2016). IDR is also said to provide more applicable solutions (Carayol & Thi 2005). In a wider sense, IDR is described as an example of a general paradigm shift in academia from limited disciplinary expertise (Mode1) to holistic problem solving (Mode 2) (Nowotny & Scott, 2003). All the promising properties of IDR find further expression in increasing research funding and higher citation counts (Tahamtan et al., 2016).

But in between all the possible advantages that IDR can bring, there are also a number of pitfalls that need to be navigated. IDR requires operational and material continuity between collaborating fields (Alvargonzalez, 2011), and it requires more coordination

(Yegros-Yegros et al., 2015; Bromham et al. 2016). Additionally, different scientific traditions hinder proper and consistent evaluation of interdisciplinary outputs that often fail to address the disciplinary criteria of excellence (Huutoniemi, 2010). And finally, prevailing incentive and evaluation patterns make it much more difficult for interdisciplinary researchers to pursue a successful career (Rhoten & Parker, 2004).

Interdisciplinarity should therefore be treated with some caution. However, it would be wrong to see the dangers of IDR as a motivation for more disciplinary research. Rather, the dangers require a systematic approach to the subject. Only then can the promises of IDR actually come true. To support this strategic approach, we propose that IDR be understood as a set of five challenges/dilemmas. Based on a systematic literature review, we have developed this conceptualization in order to point out the weaknesses of the concept and thus create a guideline for a hopefully successful implementation. After outlining our methodology (2), we specify the five dilemmas of IDR (3). Namely the ‘Definition Dilemma’ (3.1), the ‘Evaluation Dilemma’ (3.2), the ‘Impact Dilemma’ (3.3), the ‘Path-Dependence Dilemma’ (3.4) and the ‘Single Phenomenon Dilemma’ (3.5). Eventually, we discuss the dilemmas and draw a conclusion (4).

2 METHODOLOGY

IDR is a topic that received coverage in all kinds of research fields ranging from business communication (Lowry et al., 2004) to physics (Morfill and Ivlev, 2009). We thus cannot define a cannon of relevant journals to include in a review. Rather, to review publications on IDR we needed to look for publications on the topic across all academic field. To do so we ran the query (TS="interdisciplinarity" OR TS="research collaboration" OR TS="team science" OR TS="transdisciplinarity" OR TS="multidisciplinarity") AND LANGUAGE: (English) at the Web of Science core collection for the period 1990 to 2017. The database was selected due to its comprehensive nature and broad academic acceptance. We chose the search terms because we found during an earlier expert poll that these terms were often used synonymously in spite of their formal definitions. The topic category (TS) was chosen as it identifies the search terms if they are contained in either the title, the abstract or the related keywords, providing a fine-grained search unit. Prior to 1990 there were hardly any publications on the topic. That is why we set this starting point for the review. The query identified 5016 individual documents. Furthermore, we ran the same query at the Palgrave Communications database. This database was added due to the publication of a special issue on the topic interdisciplinarity in 2016, providing 28 relevant texts. This lead us to a total of 5385 texts (including duplicates) for a first screening. The titles and abstracts of these documents were then manually screened, duplicates were removed and the selection was refined for thematic fit, resulting in 460 texts. These texts were then fully assessed and the selection was further refined to our final selection of 142 documents. Besides 137 articles, 5 books were included due to their frequent coverage and widely recognized relevance for the topic in

the identified articles. The annual distribution of the final selection is presented in figure 1.

To systematically analyze the documents we employed qualitative coding with the software atlas.ti. The coding scheme was determined inductively in order to also capture initially unknown aspects. Over time we iteratively condensed our coding categories to allow for an article length synthesis.

Figure 1: Distribution of articles in review over time

3 THE FIVE DILEMMAS OF IDR

The analysis of the literature has shown us that the debates on IDR are marked by constant contradictions and tensions. These tensions combine the opportunities offered by IDR with the pitfalls inherent in this form of academic research. In many articles on the subject, however, the tensions are not analysed by both sides, but in more detail and often lopsided. Our review allows us to zoom out and to conceptualize the topic in a holistic way, so that the tensions clearly come to light and offer themselves as a structuring element to better understand what makes IDR so challenging.

3.1 The Definition Dilemma

The Definition Dilemma: There is a vivid debate about the definition of IDR. Even though there is general agreement in regards to distinct key elements of the term, many conceptual uncertainties remain. This unclear definition causes different expectations and is a potential pitfall for collaborations.

There are many diverging definitions of IDR. Often the term is presented in distinction to multidisciplinary research (MDR) and transdisciplinary research (TDR) (e.g., Aboelela et al. 2007; Choi & Pak 2006; Stokols et al. 2008a; van den Besselaar & Heimeriks 2001; Wagner et al. 2011). The most cited definition in our reviewed documents comes from the national academies:

“Interdisciplinary research (IDR) is a mode of research by teams or individuals that integrates information, data, techniques, tools, perspectives, concepts, and/or theories from two or more disciplines or bodies of specialized knowledge to advance fundamental understanding or to solve problems whose solutions are beyond the scope of a single discipline or field of research practice” (National Academies, 2005)

In contrast, MDR “involves teams of scientists approaching a problem from their own discipline” (Graff, 2011), while TDR “denotes a knowledge process that transcends and crosses disciplinary boundaries, and entails a major reconfiguration of

disciplinary divisions within an all-encompassing perspective” (Darbellay et al., 2014). The only decisive difference between the three concepts lies in the degree of knowledge integration (Wagner et al. 2011), which is – as we will argue in the “Evaluation Dilemma” (3.2) – hard to determine (especially beforehand). Team science is a necessary condition for MDR, IDR, and TDR (Stokols et al., 2008a). Some even go one step further and describes MDR, IDR, and TDR as different modes of team science (Fiore, 2008; Hall et al., 2008a).

When zooming in, it get even more complicated: researchers could be interdisciplinary in one dimension (e.g., data) while being ‘only’ multidisciplinary in another (e.g., methodology). This raises the question how integrated knowledge has to be in order to label a research process, researcher, journal, or entire field as interdisciplinary. For this reason, some authors differentiate between different types and modes of IDR. Siedlock and Hibbert (2014) for example describe four such modes of integration: (1) Sourcing, where methods and tools are borrowed; (2) consolidating, where methods and tools become core elements; (3) configuring, where instruments of different disciplines are merged, and (4) synergizing where new tools are created with the help of joint knowledge. Other authors are less concerned with the degree of integration in their classification than with the origin of the knowledge in question. In this context Abramo et al. (2017) distinguish between specific and generic IDR and Robinson (2008) introduces the term issue-driven IDR.

Overall, this is a fundamental definitional problem since the term interdisciplinarity entails a range of very different concepts which are often talked about as if they were just one (Cooper, 2013). In consequence, IDR has several conceptual weak spots (Klein, 2008). That’s why, when talking about IDR, one should be more detailed, specifying the areas of interdisciplinary activity in the most precise way possible. This would allow a much more profound debate. Since the definition of the key term poses such a big problem, indicators are uncertain and the debate on the term tends to simplify, it is plausible that also its measurement is difficult.

3.2 The Evaluation Dilemma

The Evaluation Dilemma: The problem of definition is also reflected in the formation of indicators, which often do not grasp the complexity of IDR. These frequently come to contradictory results based on their focus, underlying data and calculations.

There are manifold indicators to measure interdisciplinarity, which are focussed on different levels and are based on different data [and calculations]. But, the measurement poses four major challenges.

Firstly, “the most appropriate indicators differ according to the level of analysis, whether it be areas, categories or journals (Morillo et al., 2001). Moreover, institutional IDR has been in the center of attention (Cassi et al., 2017). As some studies show, the results are not always congruent. At times, categories or journals of an area

are categorized interdisciplinary while the area itself is not or vice versa.

Secondly, in order to measure the knowledge exchange between disciplines, authors and/or their work need to be categorized and their disciplinary affiliation has to be determined. This can happen in several ways. Some countries such as Italy publish national databases with researcher affiliations (e.g., Abramo et al., 2012, 2013, 2014a, 2014b, 2017). Another possibility is to use institute affiliation or record history in disciplinary journals (Bergmann et al., 2017) as proxy. Others try to determine disciplinary affiliation with interviews (Brew, 2008). On the article level in particular subject categories (i.e., ISI and WOS) (Leydesdorff & Rafols, 2009) and sophisticated content-based (van Raan, 2005; Wang et al., 2013; Van den Besselaar & Heimeriks, 2006) or algorithmic approaches (Rafols & Leydesdorff, 2009; Sayam & Akaishi, 2012) are popular. Since there is also no uniform recording here, the results can vary greatly depending on the method used.

Thirdly, it is also a problem to map the extent of interaction between scientists and disciplines. While it can be presumed that an exchange of ideas is reflected by co-authorship and co-citations (e.g., Tijssen, 1992)¹, this process can also happen elsewhere. For example, the introduction of knowledge from different disciplines can be stimulated by research conferences, academic and private debates or the lecture of non-quoted literature. In addition, current indicators cannot measure the actual level of knowledge exchange. Specifically, the composition of co-authors often does not always reflect who was actually involved in a project (Bozeman & Youtie, 2015; Ponomariov & Boardman, 2016). In particular established researchers are often listed to boost citation counts.

Fourthly, a problem is the degree of integration of knowledge. This is specifically problematic since this process can only be guessed but not determined with certainty. Saying, also a single researcher introducing knowledge from a different field to a discipline and interpreting it from a disciplinary perspective could – theoretically – conduct interdisciplinary research on its own without any indicator noticing it. On the contrary, collaborating researchers from different disciplines are on many instances labeled interdisciplinary even though they are actually only multidisciplinary. For this reason many authors need to rely on working definitions for their measurement experiments. Bordons et al. (1999) for example state: “For the purpose of this study, interdisciplinarity is defined as the collaboration between researchers from different fields.”

Accordingly, IDR measures indicate a rough tendency, if any, and thus have only limited informative value (Zitt, 2005). This is primarily because of the bad quality of underlying data and the extremely high data and method dependence of the results (Moreno et al., 2016)

And also the measured and the self-perception of IDR activity tend to diverge (e.g., Brew 2008). Boix Mansilla and others’ interview study shows that researchers evaluate success in ID very differently from common indicators (2016). Following this line of argument, measuring IDR is problematic. Is it different with the determination of the impact?

¹ For a discussion see Marx & Bornmann (2016).

3.3 The Impact Dilemma

The Impact Dilemma: The Impact Dilemma: IDR is attributed to a range of potential impacts. It is often assumed that IDR is generally advantageous and that it hence has to be promoted in every possible way. However, the impact dimensions of IDR are manifold, often hard to grasp and not always positive.

In academia there are many things that are referred to as outputs such as publications, citations, conference, and other presentations. However, these factors are not exhaustible and by that “represent closure on only a small number of questions” (Renwick, 2016). Depending on the time frame and setting, IDR comes with a range of side-effects, which should be part of the equation when assessing the impact of IDR.

Quantitative impact assessment of IDR is – like the evaluation of IDR itself – difficult. Previous studies on the relationship of IDR and scientific impact have led to diverging results, due to different IDR indicators and different disciplinary foci. One finding however is mostly confirmed: “when conceptualized and operationalized using cited references, strictly disciplinary research typically receives a lower number of citations” (Chen et al., 2015a). Yet, there are certain exceptions. Larivière & Gringas (2010) find that highly disciplinary and highly interdisciplinary articles tend to have a low impact based on citations. Supportingly, Yegros-Yegros et al. (2015) claim that very high and very low degrees of IDR decrease citation impact. In another study Larivière et al. add however, that interdisciplinary co-authors in the majority of cases equally benefit in terms of citation impact (2015). Uzzi et al. (2013) specify that primarily those disciplinary combinations foster citations that are “anchored in substantial conventionality, not novelty, while mixing in a left tail of combinations that are rarely seen together”. In an analysis of mono- and multidisciplinary publications in WOS and Scopus Levitt & Thelwall (2008) come to a different conclusion: They claim that in general multidisciplinary publications – which in many cases form the basis for interdisciplinary measures – are not more highly cited.

While Kwon et al. (2017) agree that articles which aggregate knowledge of multiple disciplines are much higher cited, they point out that, at the same time, this also leads to a lower level of funding success. This is backed by Bromham et al. (2016) who argue that interdisciplinary distance has a negative effect on funding success based on data of the Australian Research Council Discovery Programme.

Another negative effect of IDR is a reduction of output. Leahey et al. (2017) discover a “productivity penalty”. This is also confirmed for co-authorship in general, where – based on a study of Lee and Bozeman (2005) – the absolute number of articles increases, whereas the fractional count per author decreases. This sheds light on another issue. There are many studies which do not specifically refer to IDR, but assess at least potentially interdisciplinary scenarios such as the effect of co-authorship on publications (e.g., Bales et al., 2014; Bozeman & Youtie, 2015). Also the effect of network embeddedness (Gonzalez-Brambila et al., 2013) or social capital through co-authorship (Li et al., 2013; Rotolo & Petruzzelli, 2013) on research output and

quality is investigated. This raises the question of which of the factors can actually be held responsible for the increase.

However, these indicators only cover a fraction of the actual impact and the actual effects of IDR can be much more far-reaching. That is why, possibilities need to be found to explore the often noted soft effects of IDR such as providing comprehensive solutions across disciplinary boundaries (Braun & Schubert 2003), a stronger focus on industrial users and market demand (Barry et al. 2008) or more ‘breakthrough’ solutions (Carayol & Thi 2005; Yegros-Yegros et al. 2015), involving new ideas and knowledge (Choi & Pak, 2008). Specifically interview and survey studies show that the perceived effects exceed the traditionally measured ones (e.g. Måsse et al., 2008). There are many often ignored side-effects. A huge part of IDR is conducted in multidisciplinary research teams and by that stimulates debate and knowledge exchange among researchers from different disciplines. This exchange can lead to learning, which shapes the work of a scientist far beyond the actual contact (Haythornthwaite, 2006). Also, a research product could may have an interdisciplinary impact through the audiences it connects (Lynn, 2014).

Another problem of impact assessment is the disregard of the time dimension. Van den Besselaar and Hemereiks (1996) map the evolution of the discipline artificial intelligence. Originally an interdisciplinary field of computer science and psychology, it is now a discipline in its own right. This shows that successful IDR can indeed be embedded in disciplinary structures. Hence, from a long-term perspective successful IDR follows disciplinary rules. For this reason, the debate on impact assessment should focus more on the time component, since many of the named advantages and disadvantages only apply for a certain period of time. Wang et al. (2015) explicitly include time in their examination of citation behaviour. They find that while IDR has a negative effect on citations in a three year time frame, it has a positive effect in a thirteen year time frame. The more in interdisciplinary a work is, the stronger is its citation delay. Again, looking at the evolutionary process of disciplines as described earlier this appears plausible. Also, it explains changes of disciplinary affiliation over time as the investigation of the journal *Cognitive Science* demonstrates (Leydesdorff & Goldstone, 2014).

Just like IDR itself, also many of its effects are not grasped by traditional indicators. This hinders comprehensive impact assessment.

3.4 The Path-Dependence Dilemma

The Path-Dependence Dilemma: The scientific community is often unable to deal with interdisciplinary knowledge and to reward its novel input. This is primarily due to existing evaluation and incentive structures.

The example of Danish research sponsorship impressively shows how national incentives for IDR can oppose reputation incentives and thereby become ineffective (Wien et al., 2017). This becomes especially visible when turning to common evaluation criteria and incentive structures. In order to be publish an interdisciplinary article and interdisciplinary peer review needs to

take place. However most review boards remain to be highly disciplinary. It is often questionable which reviewer possesses the expertise for the assessment of interdisciplinary work (Bammer, 2016; Mansilla, 2006; McLeish & Strang, 2016). And also the standards for “good work” blur. In consequence, many reviewers use the authors’ publication history, past success in attracting competitive funding or evidence of prior successful collaboration of team members instead of the actual work to separate wheat from chaff (Bammer, 2017). Considering the innovative role IDR is meant to play, this is paradox since it fosters sorting out genuinely novel work, manifesting existing structures further. This also highlights the distinct role of journals in this process. Hellsten and Leydesdorff (2016) show that certain disciplinary collaborations are fostered by editorial focus and Manana Rodriguez (2017) even categorizes journals as either knowledge-importing or knowledge exporting.

Also publication requirements by universities prevent IDR. Specifically, business schools request publications in highly ranked journals. Since those journals are primarily of disciplinary nature, researchers need to conduct disciplinary research to advance their careers and to keep their positions (Rafols et al. 2012; Carayol & Thi, 2005). In this context many studies claim that interdisciplinary research careers tend to be less successful (Rhoten & Parker, 2004). This is also due to the fact that disciplines possess varying reward structures and publication standards. For example, an extensive list of co-authors is common in the natural sciences, while it isn’t in the social sciences. Also the meaning of the order of authors differs between the disciplines, which can lead to dispute (Campbell, 2005). Another problem constitutes the disciplinary socialization of the researchers. Lynn (2014) points out that research preferably cite from their own field since they learned to do so. Hence, there are distinct educational barriers (Clark & Wallace, 2015).

These examples show, that science is highly path depended. The current structures are established to foster disciplinary, not IDR. This needs to be taken into account

3.5 The Single Phenomenon Dilemma

The Single Phenomenon Dilemma: IDR is frequently treated as a single phenomenon. By that, environmental, individual, and disciplinary differences are not sufficiently addressed. Yet, these differences severely affect the way in which research collaboration is possible.

IDR enhancement strategies are primarily focused on fund allocation, the installation of steering structures such as interdisciplinary research units and changing recruitment and evaluation processes (e.g., Sa 2008; Adams et al., 2007). These efforts address all disciplines equally and focus on a structural level. However, many studies highlight that disciplines differ significantly in their interdisciplinary collaboration behaviour. In addition, certain personal attributes affect interdisciplinarity and hence need to be taken into account.

Abramo et al. (2013) find that different disciplines have different propensities to collaborate. While for example intramural collaboration of mathematicians computer scientists, economists

and statisticians remains low, it is extremely high for civil, industrial and information engineers. This can be explained by differences in the accessibility of interdisciplinarity. While some disciplines have “bad access” to IDR (i.e., humanities and social sciences; Pedersen, 2016), others tend to establish relations with other disciplines quite easily (i.e., Biomedicine and technology (Morillo et al. 2003). This results in huge disciplinary differences in terms of their interdisciplinary character and the tools they respond to (Sans-Mendez et al. 2001; Wang et al. 2017). Support measures should be adapted accordingly.

However, there are also certain individual factors that shape interdisciplinarity. Abramo et al. (2014) point out that collaboration behaviour depends on academic rank. Moreover, collaboration behaviour in Australia seems to be positively influenced by the number of prior Australian and foreign university jobs, the holding of an international citizenship and a personal orientation toward applied research (Woolley et al. 2015). Ribeiro (2016) claims that personal ties are more relevant for research collaboration than systemic ones (i.e., through a research center) while systemic factors such as department affiliation can in fact decrease interdisciplinarity. Rhoten and Pfirman (2007) find that female researchers are more interdisciplinary than their male peers. These differences need to be taken into account when scouting for successful IDR implementation.

Besides these rather isolated factors, it especially needs to be accounted for interpersonal dynamics. Rafols (2007) finds that the goal of a research project has a much stronger influence on interdisciplinarity than the disciplinary origin the researchers. Hence, IDR requires researchers to “have some additional skills beyond their contributory” (Andersen, 2016). Researchers need to be able to communicate effectively and to develop team dynamics. This also explains the many points of overlap with team science (e.g., Fiore 2008; Hall et al. 2008a). For this reason, it seems obvious that IDR needs to be practiced consciously and actively (Darbellay, 2015).

Overall, the promotion of IDR should also be strongly aligned with the targeted disciplines, institutions and individuals and hence account for differences. A general approach is not suitable.

4 CONCLUSION OF REVIEW

Our review shows that IDR is a major challenge for all involved parties. This begins with the definition of the term, which can lead to different researchers with very different expectations going into a research project, with which later conflicts are inevitable. The challenge of an unclear concept is further aggravated by the fact that there is disagreement about the evaluation of IDR. In a research landscape that relies more and more on quantitative indicators, the lack of clarity about how to measure IDR is causing further confusion and therefore general scepticism about IDR on the part of researchers. And as if that were not enough, the conceptualization of the impact of IDR also offers a great need for discussion. It is unclear where, when, and in what form this impact can be expected. This becomes a challenge especially in the light of our fourth dilemma, because despite all interdisciplinary projects, the research system is and remains fundamentally

disciplinary. Careers are first and foremost made disciplinary and thus interdisciplinary successes must always be translated for one's own discipline in order not to exclude appreciation from the outset. And finally, IDR suffers from the fact that a large number of very different projects, ideas, and structures are subsumed under the same term.

Taken together, the five dilemmas show the full range of challenges facing interdisciplinary projects. If one compares this with the possible advantages, it is understandable why most researchers concentrate on disciplinary research projects. IDR can be conceptualized as "high-risk / high-reward" research (Leahey et al., 2017) that cannot rely on established structures but requires a continuous negotiation process in every single project. Only if this negotiation process is conducted consistently can IDR successfully generate new knowledge. The five dilemmas cannot solve this negotiation process, but they can show the arenas in which it must take place. On the one hand, this understanding on the part of research funders and scientific institutes is necessary in order to treat IDR projects not all equally, but all differently. On the other hand, the dilemma points to the challenges that researchers have to negotiate with each other when setting up IDR projects. Only in this way can later frustrations be limited and project success become more likely. In addition to all the challenges that IDR poses, the possible successes that make this kind of scientific collaboration possible should motivate more researchers to take on the challenge of IDR.

5 FURTHER STEPS: A METHODOLOGY FOR EFFICIENT EXPLORATION OF LOCAL BIBLIOMETRIC DATABASES AND AUTOMATIC DETECTION OF INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH

An applied wing of this project was aimed at enabling easy preprocessing, exploration, and serendipitous knowledge discovery (Darbellay et al., 2014). In bibliometric datasets, especially for – but not limited to– the purpose of profiling and investigating interdisciplinary research. Although the literature study detailed in the previous sections of this report is rather loosely connected to this methodological study, some of the techniques used in the latter study is likely to be helpful when the conceptual framework outlined by the of the literature study needs to be validated via a bibliometric dataset. In this section, we briefly describe this methodology.

5.1 An Automated Data Preprocessing and Visual Exploration Platform for Studies of Interdisciplinarity

In order to create a reusable data preprocessing and enrichment system for bibliographic datasets, we developed Python modules² for (1) cleaning and parsing of various data formats that hold bibliographic information, such as BIB and CSV files, (2) reformatting the entries imported from these sources (e.g., converting author names into a standard format), and (3) outputting the processed entries as RDF³ files. After the conversion, this data was queried using a SPARQL⁴ endpoint, and automated queries were run to enrich the datasets using either other RDF files imported in the same way, or via endpoints such as of OpenCitations.net.

Following the preprocessing and enrichment steps, the resulting data was made available on the web by using a user-friendly interface, Linked Data Reactor⁵—another system that is being actively developed by a member⁵ of our research team, Ali Khalili. By requiring no technical skills for data exploration, visualization, and preliminary data analysis, use of LD-R is intended for making the data accessible to the entirety of our team and collaborators during this study. (An overview of the system can be viewed in Figure 2.)

Figure 2: The automated data preprocessing and enrichment system used in the study.

5.2 Follow-up Study

At the time of this report, the aforementioned database creation and enrichment functionality is in place and some annotation features such as automatic keyword extraction from abstracts are also implemented.

As a follow-up to this study after the completion of the Network Institute Academy Assistant project, we are currently developing a methodology for automatic detection of interdisciplinary topics in bibliometric databases using metadata such as author keywords, Web of Science Categories⁶, and annotations retrieved from DBpedia⁷. At the essence of our methodology lies the creation of

² The Python libraries developed for the project can be found at <https://github.com/clokman/KFIR>

³ RDF is a file format that holds a graph-like representation of the data and is compatible with semantic web technologies.

⁴ A language that allows querying RDF files.

⁵ For the home page of Linked Data Reactor, see: <http://ld-r.org/>

⁶ Web of Science (WoS) categories are a relatively new construct in the WoS database. They are derived from the older ISI (Institute for Scientific Information) subject

categories, and serve as a lower level construct that is used to categorize entities of the database into 365 scientific fields.

⁷ The annotation module of Linked Data Reactor is able to use the DBpedia Spotlight service (<https://www.dbpedia-spotlight.org/>)—an automatic text annotation tool that checks texts against a semantic representation of Wikipedia—to retrieve annotations from abstracts of articles, and add them to articles as additional metadata. During this operation, a 0.5 confidence ratio was selected for DBpedia annotation tool—a

topic co-occurrence graph/network using such metadata (i.e., if two topics are present in an article as indicated by the article metadata, these two topics are connected to each other in our graph via a 'co_occurred' link, and the weight of this connection is incremented with each co-occurrence). Once a co-occurrence network (i.e., typically a medium-sized graph with a few million connections between several thousands of topics) is in place, we run graph algorithms on within this network to calculate the degree of interdisciplinary of each topic. Notably, calculating betweenness centralities of nodes in this network proved to be an effective way of accomplishing this objective, following the methodology outlined by (Leydesdorff, 2007; Rafols & Meyer, 2010). Betweenness centrality is a graph algorithm that measures how many shortest paths between all the other nodes pass through a given node, and therefore calculates the number of times that a node plays a connector role between the clusters of nodes in the graph. And this method, rather intuitively, can also be applied to calculating how much a particular topic is located in-between other topics, and this, in turn, can be used to estimate the level of interdisciplinarity of a topic (i.e., its ability to serve as a bridge between different disciplinary clusters). Once this statistic is calculated for each node, passing this interdisciplinarity score to the articles, journals, and authors that often publish about the topics that has a high score (or recently published many times on these topics, if the interest is current trends) becomes a trivial issue.

We are currently finished with the development of this methodology, and the initial results indicate that it is not only a successful method but also one that can work on small datasets⁸. This gives it a unique advantage over the most commonly used methodology in studies of interdisciplinarity and of scientometrics: analyzing the publication landscape with citation networks. Although being the de-facto method, citation analysis requires very large datasets, such as those provided by Web of Science or Scopus, whose yearly membership costs can exceed 100,000 Euros. Therefore, our method could be one of the first that can be used to detect interdisciplinary in small bibliometric databases, and lower the entry threshold for studies of interdisciplinarity, and for scientometrics research in general.

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conservative parameter value that allows filtering in only the annotations that were likely to be accurately interpreted (e.g., interpretation of the word 'study' as the act of studying a topic by a student in a library versus a scientific study of a topic by a research team, depending on the context).

⁸ For our analyses, we used the Pure databases, as well as a local subset of Web of Science database for Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam and Universiteit van Amsterdam. These datasets consisted about 100,000 to 150,000 articles.

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